

METHODS OF USING THE CASE STUDY METHOD IN LIFE SAFETY COURSES

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Abstract: this article describes the methods of conducting "Safety of life activity" classes using the case study method. The purpose of our research is to use the case-study method to educate students, to understand science, and to develop professional competencies in students by forming the qualities of ingenuity, curiosity, enthusiasm, and creativity. In the introduction of the article, the effective work being carried out in the field of personnel training in our country is highlighted, and some shortcomings in the education system are mentioned. In the section of literature analysis and methods: the recommendations given by them using textbooks, training manuals and published scientific articles written by scientists of our country and developed countries are reflected. In the results and discussion part: the achievements achieved during the training of students in the subject of "Safety of life activities" through the case-study method that we recommend are presented. In the conclusion, recommendations on the use of the case study method are given based on the studied literature and methods. The last part of the article contains a list of used literature.

Key words: case study, method, training, expert, personnel, lecture, practical, laboratory, seminar, professional competence.

INTRODUCTION

It is no exaggeration to say that it is important to fundamentally reform the personnel training system in higher education institutions at a time when all fields are developing in the world today. Because knowledgeable and competent personnel is the foundation of the new Uzbekistan.

In particular, the establishment of a new Uzbekistan of our president is not just a wish, a subjective phenomenon, but the existing political-legal, socio-economic, spiritual-educational situation in our country, which has fundamental historical foundations. His words are worthy of praise.

In all higher education institutions operating in our country, new teaching methods are used in the process of imparting knowledge and training to future specialists. An example of this is interactive methods. Experiences in using the right interactive methods have entered the educational process of HEIs. However, the use of the case study method, which is one of the interactive methods, has not yet become

popular. Case study is one of the most effective interactive methods in personnel training.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Methods and means of solving practical situations, i.e. case-study (English "case"-collective, specific practical, case, study-training) technology, which is taken from the life of an organization, group of people or individuals. means a real situation. Gary Thomasque provides a case study: Case studies are the analysis of individuals, events, decisions, periods, projects, laws, organizations, and other systems that have been previously studied through one or more methods. The subject of the case is analytical situations, and the object is the process of its analysis [5].

Case study technology was first used in 1870 at Harvard Business School. As for the term "problem" (situation), this word has been used more in the fields of medicine and law, and in the educational system this word is interpreted in a new way. In 1920, Harvard Business School (HBS) teachers, relying on the teaching experience of lawyers, chose analysis and discussion of concrete situations in economic practice as the main method of education, and this teaching method began to be widely used [4].

Russian scientists G.A.Bryansky, Yu.Yu.Ekaterinoslavsky, O.V.Kozlova, Yu.D.Krasovsky, V.Ya.Platonov, D.A.Pospelov, O.A.Ovsyannikov, V.S.Rapoppornik conducted scientific researches, but during this period, insufficient attention was paid to this method, and due to pressure from various social strata, this technology was not used in teaching processes. In the second half of the 1990s, the case-study technology was re-examined by Russian experts in the field of economics. As a result of this, students in the field of economy developed independent and correct decision-making, creative qualities, and professional skills.

A.I.Urdinov, A.M.Khakimov use the case-study method in the process of preparing future lawyers and emphasize that the result was positive. In addition, they say that this method is becoming popular today, and it is effective to use it in the educational process of HEIs [3].

"Case-study" technology (see "case" - from chemo, method, "study" - problem situation; situational analysis or analysis of problem situations) - 1) to help students find the most optimal options by analyzing a concrete, real problem situation technology that serves to form skills; 2) teaching technique used in describing real situations.

The main tasks of technology are as follows: 1. Development of analytical skills and critical thinking; 2. Ensuring unity of theory and practice; 3. Demonstrating different views and approaches to the problem; 4. Decision-making and its consequences; 5. providing feedback on; 6. Alternative in case of uncertainties; 7. Formation of options evaluation skills [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our research, we conducted audience training on "Safety of life activities" using the case study method. In the course of our research, a case adapted to the topic of each training was used. That is, as follows:

Type of case used in training: "Mini" structural structures:

1. Statement of the case (problem).
2. Tasks (or questions) related to solving a case (problem).
3. List of literature for use.
4. Methodological instructions.
5. The process of solving the case (promoting analysis and solution options, checking the acceptability of options).
6. Organizing a presentation on the solution of the case.
7. Analysis of the case solution.
8. The solution of the teacher (caseologist).

Case report: How can you assess accidents in production (see picture)?

1. Questions about solving the case (problem):

- 1) Explain the causes of accidents that may occur in production?
- 2) What should be done to prevent accidents that may occur in production?

2. List of literature for use:

1) Yuldashev O.R. Special course on labor protection./ Textbook. - T.: "Wing of Thought", 2015. - 336 p.

2) E.I.Ibragimov, S.Gazinazarova, O.R.Yuldashev. Special course on labor protection. Textbook.-T.: TIMI, 2014.-536 p.

3) O.R. Yuldashev, Sh.G. Djabborova, O.T. Khasanova. Life safety. Textbook - T.: "Tashkent-Economics", 2014. - 268 p.

4) Yormatov G.Yo. and others. Life safety. - T.: "Alokachi", 2009. - 348 p.

5) Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Labor Protection" (new edition). September 22, 2016.

3. Methodological instructions:

before answering the case questions, compare your information with the sentences given in the given literature; answer after you are sure;

write down the answers to case questions in your notebook so that you don't forget them when you find them in the literature;

explain the answer to the questions with real-life examples, this is also taken into account during the evaluation;

try to answer the questions before your teammates;

4. The process of solving the case (promoting analysis and solution options, checking the acceptability of options).

The leader of the lesson evaluates after summarizing and analyzing the answers given by the students to the case questions.

5. Organizing a presentation on the solution of the case. At the end, the leader of the session will show the presentation of his solution to the given case questions to the students, i.e.:

Answer to Case Question 1: According to W. H. Heinrich (1931), who developed the domino theory, 88 percent of all accidents are caused by dangerous human actions, 10 percent by dangerous actions, and 2 percent by "acts of God." He proposed a "five-factor sequence of accidents" in which each factor triggers the next step in a domino fashion. The sequence of factors of the accident is as follows:

1. social environment; 2. fault of the worker; 3. dangerous action with mechanical and physical danger; 4. the incident occurred; 5. Injury[6]. In addition, accidents can be caused by the fault of the "Labor protection and technical safety" guide in enterprises. That is, it may be the reason that he did not instruct newly arrived and working employees on the technical safety rules related to labor protection.

Case question 2: In order to prevent accidents in production, the head of the enterprise, supervisor of labor protection of the enterprise, heads of departments, shifts, and workshops should give instructions to the workers in accordance with the rules of the procedure established by the law and by-laws. It is important that they control the time z.

In order to prevent accidents, the preliminary instructions given by the labor protection supervisor of the enterprise, the head of the periodic department or the head of the workshop, the shift supervisors, according to the legal procedure, are on time (the introduction instruction is given before the order is issued, the work training on the first working day, periodic training in 3-6 months) should be carried out effectively (see the picture).

Figure 1. The procedure for conducting instruction in workplaces.

It can be seen from the development of the lesson using the above-mentioned case-study method that during the training, it provides students with mobility, increases their thinking ability and creative qualities, and gives them the opportunity to study science in depth.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of the case-study method in the training of the science of "Life safety" is a perfect study of this science, that is, various risks that may occur in enterprises, emergency situations occur. movement, strengthens the knowledge of emergency first aid to the wounded.

In particular, we express the advantages of the case study method as follows:

case-study helps not only to solve science-related puzzles, but also to solve problems related to specialization;

the use of the case-study method in each subject ensures the quality of the lessons;

helps to reveal undiscovered aspects in students;

forms the characteristics of self-criticism in future specialists, and as a result, creates an opportunity to develop professional competence.

It is more appropriate to achieve the goal if the case-study method is used based on the following:

- if the case assignment given to students is focused on the solution of the problems witnessed in practice;

- if every student's opinion is taken into account and listened carefully to find a solution to the case assignment;

- if the students who have a correct approach to solving each case task and whose answer is clear are encouraged in time.

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